

PRAGMALINGUISTIC ANALYSIS AS MODERN STUDY IN FICTION LITERARY TRANSLATION

Irina ZYUBINA, Professor, PhD (Doctor of Philology)
(Southern Federal University, Russian Federation)

iazyubina@sfedu.ru, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1265-8366>

Received: May 24, 2025 | Reviewed: June 2, 2025 | Accepted: June 5, 2025

UDC 81 | DOI from Zenodo

The research is devoted to a new approach to the fiction literature translation study based on the analysis of the speech behavior of Vladimir Nabokov and the translators of his novel “Lolita”. The methodological basis of the study is a pragmalinguistic experiment with elements of modified content analysis. The study was conducted within the framework of Implicit Pragmalinguistics. To analyze the original text and its translations, the implicit speech strategy “Participation / non-participation of communicants in a speech event” was chosen. The main conclusion: translators should minimize their interference so that addressees see the author's intention, and not the translator's individuality.